

THE INFLUENCE MECHANISM OF TRABECULAR RADIUS AND HEIGHT OF CORE STRUCTURE ON THE COMPRESSIVE PROPERTIES OF BEETLE ELYTRON PLATES

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ABSTRACT

Two dimensionless parameters, $\eta = r_t/L$ and $\beta = h/T$, were used to investigate the influence mechanism of the trabecular radius and height of the core structure on the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity of beetle elytron plates (BEPs). The results indicated that 1) As η increases, the mechanical properties of the BEPs initially improve rapidly and then shift to a slow-changing stage, whereas with decreasing β , the mechanical properties first exhibit a slow improvement and then shift to a rapid improvement. The optimal intervals of the structural parameters in the BEPs are as follows: $0.15 < \eta < 0.25$ and $10 < \beta < 20$. The compressive strength and energy dissipation of the BEPs in this interval are more than 2 and 3.5 times that of honeycomb plates, respectively. 2) The interactive mechanism between the trabeculae and the honeycomb wall structures in BEPs was revealed within the above-described interval: the trabeculae restrain the convex deformation of the honeycomb wall, which in turn provides lateral strut support for the trabeculae. 3) A value of $\eta = 0.1$ is sufficient to enhance the mechanical properties of the sandwich plate from the 'honeycomb plate' level to the 'BEP' level, a capability that is expected to receive attention in the development of new types of lightweight, high-strength, energy-dissipating plates. Thus, it is inferred that the existence of the trabeculae in beetle elytra impart mechanical properties at the 'BEP' level to enable the biological functions of facilitating flight and protecting the body of the insect.

1 INTRODUCTION

The collisions and impacts that occur in various types of collisions pose a tremendous threat to the safety of human lives and property. Therefore, structures [1-3] that offer high deformation energy dissipation capabilities are in high demand due to their crashworthiness and impact resistance. A type of lightweight, high-strength structure used for this purpose is the honeycomb plate [4-6]. The biological prototype for an honeycomb plate is a honeycomb. Commercially available honeycomb sandwich plates are currently manufactured by adhesively or mechanically joining their skin and core components, which are produced separately using different processes [7]. Providing an alternative inspiration from nature, various species of beetles have survived since the age of the dinosaurs. Through their long evolution process, beetle elytra have developed a remarkable biological structure that exhibits several unique biological functions. For example, the structural color from the surfaces of beetle elytra is a typical instance of the combination of a subtle fine structure and camouflage [8-10]. In addition, the inner three-dimensional structure of elytra, which imparts biological functions such as protection of the main body of the insect and the facilitation of flight, is hypothesized to be an advanced evolutionary biological structure that is both lightweight and high strength and exhibits excellent impact-dissipating performance [11-13]. Experiments on the beetle elytron plate (BEP), based on the features of a trabecular-honeycomb structure (THS) proposed by JX Chen according to the elytra of the *A. dichotoma* beetle, have directly verified this hypothesis [14]. Recently, the

forementioned shared mechanism was verified by a series of experiments that comparing BEPs and honeycomb plates [15]. Furthermore, the effects of the core volume, wall thicknesses, honeycomb in-plane dimensions and forming methods on the mechanical properties of BEPs have been investigated to demonstrate the superiority of the structure and mechanical properties of BEPs relative to those of honeycomb plates and to clarify the essential relationship between the biological structure and its function [16].

In previous experiments, the selected dimensions and corresponding structural parameters of the BEPs, particularly those of the THS, were determined by experience, the influence mechanism of the structural parameters on the mechanical properties of BEPs has not been investigated. Qiang Chen [17], to a certain extent, presented a parameter optimization design process and relevant conclusions for the THS (only the core structure, rather than the sandwich plate consisting of the THS along with the upper and lower skins). According to the previous research, in their core structures, the essence of the compressive strength of BEPs or honeycomb plates is the stability problem of the thin plate or the shell structure under vertical load, while the ratio of height-to-thickness is the key factor affecting the stability of the components. Therefore, two dimensionless parameters are adopted here to investigate the influence mechanism of the trabecular radius and height of the THS on the compressive strength, energy dissipation capacity, and interactive mechanism between trabeculae and honeycomb wall structures in BEPs. This research provides a further theoretical basis for the design and application of BEPs in practical engineering.

2 EXPERIMENTAL AND MODELING METHODS

2.1 MODEL DESIGN

The experimental samples of sandwich plates are shown in Fig. 1, where L is the honeycomb unit dimension (the distance between the central points in adjacent trabeculae is 16 mm), r_t is the outer radius of the trabecula (hereafter referred to as the radius), T is the wall thickness of the core structure ($T = 1$ mm), h is the height of the core structure, H is the total height of the sandwich plates, and both the upper and lower skins thicknesses are 2 mm. For comparison with the results of Chen *et al* [19], two dimensionless parameters, $\eta = r_t/L$ and $\beta = h/T$, are adopted to investigate the influence mechanism of the trabecular radius and the height of the core structure on the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity of BEPs. Based on the previous experimental model ($\eta = 0.25$, $\beta = 16$), we add the experimental samples with $\eta = 0$ (honeycomb plate), 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, and 0.4 (here, $\beta = 16$) and $\beta = 11, 21, 26$, and 31 (here, $\eta = 0.25$), and the comparable samples of the honeycomb plates are assigned for each β . A ProJet model machine, manufactured by 3D Systems (South Carolina, U.S.), was used to print these experimental samples.

Fig. 1 Dimensions and structures of the sandwich plates: (a) overall dimensions; (b) core structure (THS) of a BEP; (c) core structure of a honeycomb plate; (d) the trabecula in the BEP. In the figure, the thickness of the trabecular strut is equal to that of the honeycomb walls.

2.2 EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The dimensions of the sandwich plates were designed in accordance with the requirements for standard compressive test specimens specified in the ASTM-C365-03 standard [18]. Regarding the plate, for the same reason provided in the previous paper [15], the engineering resin material was

chosen to investigate the influence of the above-described structural parameters on the mechanical properties of these structures, the 3D-printing time is at 22/11/2016. These results can provide a basis for the subsequent study of BEPs prepared by fiber reinforced plastic or metal materials. The compressive test device used was a T5105 electronic testing machine manufactured by MTS, the test models, were subjected to displacement loading at a rate of 1 mm/min. Taking into account the deformation of sandwich plate mainly occurs in the core structure rather than the upper and lower skins, the deformation energy of unit volume of the core structure (formula 1, hereafter referred to as the energy dissipation capacity, and volume of the core structure V_c was used because the material density of BEPs and honeycomb plates are same) is used as the index of the panel to evaluate its energy dissipation capacity in this paper.

$$E_c = \frac{\int_0^D F d\delta}{V_c} \quad (1)$$

where E_c is the energy absorption of unit volume of core structure; $F = \sigma A$ is the vertical load on the core structure, σ is the stress in the core structure, A is the cross-sectional area of the core structure; $\delta = \varepsilon h$ is the vertical deformation of the core structure, ε is the vertical strain in the core structure, h is the height of the core structure; $D = \varepsilon_{max} h$ is the maximum deformation of the core structure, ε_{max} is the maximum strain in the core structure; and V_c is the volume of the core structure.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Influence of the trabecular radius and height of the core structure on the compressive properties of BEPs

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the experimental results for BEPs with changes in the dimensionless parameters of $\eta = r_t/L$ and $\beta = h/T$. Following a previous report [16], the stress-strain curve can be approximately divided into four stages (I-IV). First, when $\eta = 0.2$, the BEPs undergo nearly horizontal plastic deformation (i.e., a plateau) at stage III, as described previously¹⁷. The platform stage III shortens or declines when the value of η is too high or too low. To facilitate the comparison, Fig. 2(b) shows the ratio (P_λ and $E_\lambda = \text{BEP}/\text{Honeycomb Plate}$) based on the compressive strength and the energy dissipation capacity of honeycomb plates ($\eta = 0$), respectively, which describes the multiple relationship of the mechanical properties between BEPs and honeycomb plates. In Fig. 2(b), the fitted curves, based on the ratios P_λ and E_λ , can be approximately divided into two regimes with η increasing: the fast-rising stage F and the slow-changing stage S. It can be assumed a priori that when the structural dimension of trabeculae is larger, the compressive strength is higher; however, when the compressive strengths of the corresponding structures reach a certain value, any further changes are minimal. However, the energy dissipation capacity of BEPs, limited by the compressive strength and the shortening or decline of the plateau in stage III, increases slowly or further declines after $\eta \geq 0.2$, but the values of P_λ and E_λ are over 2 and 3.7, respectively, as η ranges from 0.1 to 0.4.

Fig. 2 Experimental results of varying η : (a) stress-strain curve and (b) fitting curves based on the ratio

(P_λ and $E_\lambda = \text{BEP}/\text{Honeycomb Plate}$) in terms of compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity, respectively. The values marked in (b) is compressive strength and energy dissipation of the BEPs and honeycomb plates, respectively.

Fig. 3 The experimental results for BEPs and honeycomb plates when β is changing: (a) stress-strain curve, (b) compressive strength, (c) energy dissipation capacity, and (d) fitting curves based on the ratio (P_λ and $E_\lambda = \text{BEP}/\text{Honeycomb Plate}$) in terms of the compressive strength and the energy dissipation capacity, respectively.

Second, regarding the influence of β , value of β reach up to 31. When β is at its maximum, the mechanical properties of BEPs and honeycomb plates are at their lowest points. Thus, the experimental results were investigated from $\beta = 31$ to 11. According to the theory of elastic stability [19], as β decreases from 31 to 11, the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity of sandwich plates are predicted to improve. However, the aspect of interest here is the longer horizontal plastic deformation (a plateau) or the rising curve (β from 21 to 11) in stage III in Fig. 3 (a). As β decreases, the mechanical properties of these sandwich plates can be divided at $\beta = 21$ into two regimes (Fig. 3b, c, K_1 and K_2). With the reduction of β , the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity of sandwich plates increase slowly in the first regime (Fig. 3b, c, stage K_1) and rapidly in the second regime (K_2), and the growth rate for BEPs is faster than that of honeycomb plates. Finally, from the ratio (B/H) of the mechanical properties of the BEPs and honeycomb plates, although the ratio of compressive strength is slightly reduced (Fig. 3d, solid line), the value remains in the range of 2.2 to 2.5, which is little difference. In other words, the compressive strength of BEPs can reach over twice that of honeycomb plates. When $\beta = 21$ or less, the energy dissipation capacity of BEPs can be as high as approximately four times that of the honeycomb plates (Fig. 3d, dash line). This finding indicates that when β is an integer between 10 and 20, the mechanical properties mentioned above are improved synthetically, and this range can be denoted as the optimized interval for the structural design of BEPs.

Based on the foregoing information, regardless of the values of η and β , the compressive strength of the BEPs is always greater than twice that of the honeycomb plates, and the energy dissipation capacity is approximately four times greater, which adequately explains the superiority of

the mechanical properties of the BEPs. Thus, the BEPs can be used as a novel type of sandwich plate possessing a lightweight, high strength and high energy dissipation capacity. This superior bionic structure is expected to rely on a unique strengthening mechanism, as has been discussed preliminarily in previous reports [15, 16]. Next, in this paper, the interactive mechanism between the trabeculae and the honeycomb wall structures in BEPs will be further investigated in terms of the different deformation and failure modes of the core structure as η is varied.

3.2 The interactive mechanism between trabeculae and honeycomb wall structures in BEPs

As reported previously [16], the fundamental difference between the core structures of a BEP and a honeycomb plate is the trabeculae at the intersection of the honeycomb walls. Thus, in honeycomb plates, the intersection of the honeycomb walls is assumed to be a triangular column (Fig. 4a, represented as the yellow part of the dotted circle) for straightforward comparison with the trabeculae in the BEPs. In that manner, under vertical loads, the mechanical properties of sandwich plates are determined by both the trabeculae (triangular column) and the honeycomb walls in the core structure. According to the earlier study [16], under a vertical load, the triangular columns in the core structure of the honeycomb plates undergo torsion predominantly; by contrast, the BEP, because the trabeculae with a closed circular cross section have a high torsional stiffness, predominantly undergoes compression along with a certain amount of radial deformation. According to the theory of elastic stability in structures [19], the honeycomb walls (which can be considered as thin plates) have a high in-plane stiffness, but their out-of-plane stiffness is negligible. As observed in the honeycomb plates in the experiments, the direction of the torsion of the triangular column is perpendicular to the honeycomb walls themselves. In other words, the in-plane stiffness of the honeycomb walls cannot effectively resist the torsion of the triangular columns. Moreover, because of the minimal out-of-plane stiffness of the thin plates, the torsional deformation of triangular column will further induce out-of-plane convex deformation of the honeycomb walls. Thus, the two types of structures in honeycomb plates serve to accelerate the failure through excessive out-plane convex deformation of the honeycomb walls and torsional deformation of the triangular column, and lose their bearing capacity, as shown in the circle in Fig. 4(a). However, when $\eta = 0.2$ and 0.25 , the interactive mechanism between the trabeculae and the honeycomb wall structures in the BEPs is fully exerted: the trabeculae provide adequate restriction to the honeycomb walls to enable the core structure to generate an S-type convex deformation with three semi-waves; in turn, the honeycomb walls can effectively decrease the radial deformation (Fig. 4c, d, dashed line, star) of the trabeculae by the lateral restraint provided by the in-plane stiffness of thin plates, which maintains the integrity of the trabeculae during the deformation process (Fig. 4c, d, circle). Thus, the two types of structures in BEPs can bear the vertical load together; furthermore, the stress-strain curve exhibits an unambiguous plateau in stage III (Fig. 2a, $\eta = 0.2$ and 0.25), so that the capacity of deformation and energy dissipation is relatively favorable. When $\eta = 0.1$, although the honeycomb walls resist failure, because the radius of the trabeculae is excessively small relative to the length of the honeycomb walls (Fig. 4b, model), the trabecula is too weak to resist the deformation from the honeycomb walls; thus, the core structure in the BEPs continue to undergo C-type convex deformation with a semi-wave in accordance with the honeycomb plates (Fig. 4a, b, circle). When $\eta \geq 0.3$, the radius of the trabeculae is larger; in the opposite case, the range of the lateral restraint that honeycomb walls can provide to the trabecula is smaller, and only in the area near the honeycomb walls is the radial deformation of the trabecular structure constrained; in most areas, such as those shown in Fig. 4(e, f), the most parts oriented at an angle of 120° among the adjacent honeycomb wall cannot be constrained and undergo substantial radial deformation (Fig. 4e, f, dashed line, star), resulting in crack generation and complete structural failure.

Fig. 4 Experimental results related to the deformation and failure (at stage III) of the core structures when η changes: (a) $\eta = 0$, honeycomb plate; (b-f) BEPs with different η . At the upper left of each picture is the three-dimensional model of the unit element defined in Fig. 1 (b, c, quadrate dashed line); at the upper right is the top view and radial deformation of the trabeculae (dashed line). The star is the position of maximum radial deformation.

Thus, in the BEPs, in addition to the fundamental enhancement in terms of the mechanical properties provided by the trabeculae structure, an interactive mechanism exists between the trabeculae and the honeycomb walls: the trabeculae restrain the convex deformation of the honeycomb walls, and in turn, the honeycomb walls laterally restrain the trabeculae by in-plane stiffness. This mechanism is the reason that the BEP exhibits an almost horizontal plastic deformation (a plateau) in stage III of the stress-strain curve when $\eta = 0.2$ and features a relatively high energy dissipation capacity (Fig. 2). Even when $\beta = 11$, because the inner structure in the BEP is narrow and the trabeculae and the honeycomb walls apply mutual compressive loads during stage III, the BEP exhibits an independent rising stage in its stress-strain curve. To complement the discussion of strengthening mechanism [15], the deformation progress and failure characteristics of BEPs are integrated in this paper to further reveal the inherent interactive mechanism between the trabeculae and the honeycomb wall structures.

To summarize, when η ranges from 0 to 0.1, although the geometrical dimensions of the trabeculae are too small to alter the deformation mode of the honeycomb walls, the compressive strength and energy dissipation of the BEPs are significantly enhanced to up to 2 and 3.7 times that of

honeycomb plates, respectively. This result indicates that, although the radius r_t of the trabeculae at the intersection of the honeycomb walls is only one-tenth of the honeycomb dimension L , this size is sufficient to augment the mechanical properties of the sandwich plate from the 'honeycomb plate' level to the 'BEP' level, a fundamental improvement that exemplifies the enhancement function of the trabeculae in the sandwich plates. It is inferred that, even if the dimension of the trabeculae in the beetle elytra is tens of microns [20], this configuration will detectably enhance the compressive strength and the energy dissipation capacity to realize the function of facilitating flight and protecting the body of the insect. The specific dimensions of a BEP should be optimized according to the specific application, including the size, material, and the conditions under which it is used; this topic is beyond the discussion in this paper. However, based on the conditions used in this experiment, when the honeycomb dimension (L) and the wall thickness (T) are constant, we can report relatively favorable intervals of structure parameters: $0.15 < \eta < 0.25$ and $10 < \beta < 20$. Moreover, this study also validates the rationality of structure parameters ($\eta = 0.25$, $\beta = 16$) that were used in the earlier experiments [15, 16] and lie within the recommended ranges.

Considering only the THS, Chen Chen *et al.* proposed the optimized value of $\eta = 0.3$ to optimize the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity [17]. However, under the condition of the fully integrated BEPs in this paper, η is recommended to be 0.2. The difference is attributed to the material used in the study, in addition, the only core structure was considered in Chen Qiang's study and the entire sandwich plate in our study. The structure parameter optimization of a BEP will be further studied in the context of practical applications and reported in an upcoming paper.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two dimensionless parameters, $\eta = r_t/L$ and $\beta = h/T$, were used to investigate the influence mechanism of the trabecular radius and the height of the core structure on the compressive strength and energy dissipation capacity of BEPs. The results are summarized below.

1) With increasing η , the mechanical properties of the BEPs initially improve rapidly and then shift to a slow-changing stage; with decreasing β , the mechanical properties initially improve slowly and then shift to a rapid improvement; based on the conditions in this experiment, we determined the optimal intervals of the structural parameters as follows: $0.15 < \eta < 0.25$ and $10 < \beta < 20$. The compressive strength and the energy dissipation capacity of the BEPs are approximately 2 and 4 times than those of the honeycomb plates in this interval, respectively.

2) In the BEPs, in addition to the fundamental enhancement of the mechanical properties provided by the trabecular structure, an interactive mechanism between the trabeculae and the honeycomb walls was revealed: the trabeculae restrain the convex deformation of the honeycomb walls; and in turn, the honeycomb walls provide lateral restraint for the trabeculae. This interactive mechanism is well maintained over the intervals in conclusion 1.

3) Although the radius r_t of the trabeculae at the intersection of the honeycomb walls is only one-tenth of the honeycomb dimension L , this value is sufficient to augment the mechanical properties of the sandwich plate from the 'honeycomb plate' level to the 'BEP' level. The mechanical properties of BEPs are markedly superior to those of the honeycomb plates, and the BEPs could be fully popularized and applied as a new form of lightweight, high-strength and buffering plates. Based on this finding, it is inferred that the existence of trabeculae in the beetle elytra substantially enhance the compressive strength and the energy dissipation capacity to realize its function of facilitating flight and protecting the body of the insect.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Q. Chen, N. Pugno and K. Zhao. Mechanical properties of a hollow-cylindrical-joint honeycomb. *Compos. Struct.* **109**, 2014, pp. 68-74.

- [2] M. H. Luxner, A. Woesz and J. Stampfl. Pettermann. A finite element study on the effects of disorder in cellular structures. *Acta Biomaterialia* **5**, 2009, pp. 381-390.
- [3] L. J. Gibson, Biomechanics of cellular solids. *J. Biomech.* **38**, 2005, pp. 377–399.
- [4] Scarpa. F, Blain. S, Lew and T, Perrott. Elastic buckling of hexagonal chiral cell honeycombs. *Compos. A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, **38**, 2007, pp. 280-289.
- [5] C. Lira and F. Scarpa. Transverse shear stiffness of thickness gradient honeycombs. *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **70**, 2010, pp. 930-936.
- [6] L. J. Gibson and M. F. Ashby. *Cellular solid-structure and properties*, 2nd ed. Cambridge University Press, 1997.
- [7] G. K. Hering. Method and device for joining sections of thermoplastic continuous web material. US Patent No. 7559351B2, 2009.
- [8] H. E. Hinton and G. M. Jarman. Physiological colour change in the Hercules beetle. *Nature*, **238**, 1972, pp. 160-161.
- [9] T. D. Schultz and G. D. Bernard. Pointillistic mixing of interference colours in cryptic tiger beetles. *Nature* **337**, 1989, pp. 72-73.
- [10] H. Onslow. Metallic coloration of chrysalids. *Nature*, **108**, 1921, pp. 366–366.
- [11] D.M. Linz, A.W. Hu and M.I. Sitvarin. Functional value of elytra under various stresses in the red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum*. *Sci. Rep.*, **6**, 2016.
- [12] Q.L. Tuyen, V.T. Tien, and T.T. Hieul. How Could Beetle's Elytra Support Their Own Weight during Forward Flight? *Journal of Bionic Engineering*, **11**, 2014, pp. 529-540.
- [13] J.Y. Sun, W. Wu and C. Liu. Investigating the nanomechanical properties and reversible color change properties of the beetle *Dynastes tityus*. *J Mater Sci*, 2017, pp.1-11.
- [14] J.X. Chen, C.L. He and C.L. Gu. Compressive and flexural properties of biomimetic integrated honeycomb plates. *Mater. Des.*, **64**, 2014, pp. 214–220.
- [15] J.X. Chen, X.M. Zhang and Y. Okabe. The deformation mode and strengthening mechanism of compression in the beetle elytron plate. *Materials & Design*, **131**, 2017, pp. 481–486.
- [16] X.M. Zhang, J. Xie and J.X. Chen. The beetle elytron plate: a lightweight, high-strength and buffering functional-structural bionic material. *Sci. Rep.*, **7**, 2017, 4440.
- [17] Q. Chen, Q. Shi and S. Signetti. Plastic collapse of cylindrical shell-plate assembled periodic honeycombs under uniaxial compression: experimental and numerical analyses. *Int. J. Mech. Sci.*, **111–112**, 2016, pp. 125-133.
- [18] American Society for Testing and Materials. Standard test method for flatwise compressive properties of Sandwich cores. *ASTM-C 365-03* (2003).
- [19] S. P. Timoshenko and J. M. Gere. *Theory of Elastic Stability*, 2nd ed. McGraw-Hill, 1961.
- [20] J. X. Chen and G. Wu. Beetle forewings: epitome of the optimal design for lightweight composite materials. *Carbohydr. Polym.*, **91**, 2013, pp. 659–665.